

ABSTRACT

Climate change is a serious problem the world is facing and awareness dissemination must be a priority among educational institutions. In the Philippines, climate change education in K-12 settings may have presented a unique opportunity to make inroads toward climate literacy. However, recent studies showed that K-12 teachers avoid teaching climate change because they were uncomfortable with the subject or do not see its relevance to their curriculum. This study was focused to find out the awareness level of science and non-science teachers wabout climate change, particularly those who teach at the secondary school level. While non-science instructors were chosen using a random sample approach, science professors were chosen using purposive homogeneous sampling method. The respondents were 36 scientific teachers and 36 non-science teachers from three separate secondary schools. The researchers collected quantitative data and analyzed the level awareness on climate change among science and non-science teachers using the Awareness Assessment on Climate Change (AACC), a locally modified questionnaire validated by experts in the field. After a week of gathering data, the collected information was examined using an independent T-test, which revealed that there is no significant difference in climate change awareness among science and non-science teachers. Nonetheless, the statistics are still useful in order to continue assessing and improving the awareness of teachers of the previously mentioned problem. As a consequence of this research, an instructional brochure including truthful and realistic information concerning climate change was created.

Keywords: *Climate change awareness, science, non-science, education, assessment*

INTRODUCTION

Climate change has always been a global issue that has a wide impact on nature and all existing life on our planet. According to an updated research website article from Onion et. al. (2017), climate change is rather a long-term alteration in the climate of the Earth and weather patterns, thus, took nearly a century of research and data to convince most of the scientific community that human activity could alter the climate of our entire planet. It was also evident that several studies about the same issue, contain a lack of awareness among many people, specifically about the effect of climate change on the environment and its prevention since studies only tackle the concept and the definition of climate change according to the several studies accounted years ago.

According to the latest report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) in 2021 on their Sixth Assessment Report on The Physical Science Basis, key findings from the report included that, there was a scale of recent changes across the climate system as a whole and the present state of many aspects of the climate system but were unprecedented over many centuries to many thousands of years (Pörtner et. al., 2022). Thus, the centuries-old issue of climate change remained unknown making it possible for the world to still lack awareness about how widely spread climate change is.

In Asia, there are areas in the continent with the least capacity to respond, such as the Himalayan region and densely populated Deltas that were hit first and hardest by climate impacts (Pörtner et. al., 2022). Acknowledging the limitations in terms of capacity and coping mechanisms towards climate change, education, training, and awareness building is central to sustaining long-term capacity building (Pörtner et. al., 2022). Education has a lot more to offer in terms of improvements in addressing climate change, particularly in the climate hotspots of Asia where mostly poor, disadvantaged communities vulnerable to climate change reside (Pörtner et. al., 2022). When disseminated, climate-change awareness and information need more explanation (Pörtner et. al., 2022). It was the case since it even took years for data about climate change to be finalized and collected after a few research but the scale for its impact was still unknown if we based on the 2021 report of IPCC on the topic.

But existing research on the awareness of teachers on climate change shows a negative result from a study about prospective teachers who enter the university holding many misconceptions and misunderstandings concerning climate change (Competente, 2019).

A recent study about the awareness of pre-service teachers, concludes that pre- service teachers were unsure of how to include climate change topics since they lack the content and skill requirement to do so the study also reveals that PSTs have low awareness of climate change. And because they were to become future educators someday, the study suggested that it is a must to instill

and equip the pre-service teachers with the right mindset on climate change that will eventually make a difference in our combat against global warming (Competente, 2019).

The previously mentioned study by Competente (2019), only focuses on the study of pre-service teachers' (PSTs) views about climate change, change education, awareness of climate change, and prospective inclusion in their future courses. It was stated from the findings of their study, although climate change education in K-12 settings may have presented a unique opportunity to make inroads toward climate literacy, there were still K-12 teachers who avoid teaching climate change because they were uncomfortable with the subject or do not see its relevance to their curriculum.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to assess the climate change awareness of science teachers and non-science teachers from selected secondary schools because their knowledge would be useful inside the classroom and would help instill awareness in their students, which may help lessen the negative effects of climate change in the future.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study used a quantitative descriptive research design, which is a type of non-experimental study in which variables are assessed numerically but the variables under investigation are not changed by the researcher. The instrument of this study was a locally modified survey adopted from an existing survey questionnaire of Gazzaz and Aldeseet (2021), the Climate Change Knowledge Test or CCKT, which was previously validated by professionals related to climate change education and awareness, and was used as an instrument for their study.

Participants/Respondents. The population of this study was teachers from three selected secondary schools in Guiguinto. Using the sampling method in selecting the sample size for the study, respondents were divided into two groups, Science teachers and Non-Science teachers. Science teachers were selected using purposive sampling method resulting in a sample size of all science teachers from three selected secondary schools.

Data Analysis Procedure. The locally modified instrument of this study was called *Awareness Assessment on Climate Change* or AACC, which consists of two sections: (i) the demographic information section; and (ii) the assessment section. The demographic data of the respondents were subjected to Frequency Distribution Analysis (FDA) to obtain a quantitative result of the study. Furthermore, the statistical tool called the t-Test was used to compare the means of the two groups.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results showed that most respondents are 35 to 41 years old, with 40.28% of the overall number of respondents who participated in the study. The lowest percentage of age was found in 50 to 56 years of age, with 5.56%, which was the closest age to the compulsory retirement age of teachers in the Philippines which was from 65 to 60 years, according to an online article published by The Manila Times (Tamayo, 2022). It also implies that the majority of the respondents are female since they have the highest frequency percentage. The study shows that 18.06% of the respondents had been working as educators for at least nine years. 13.89% of the respondents had been doing so for at least ten years, and 8.33% had been doing so for at least five years. The respondent with the largest number of years in the profession—37—was also the respondent with the shortest experience—3 years. Most respondents are assigned to grade 7. Followed by grade levels 8 and 9. Furthermore, the lowest percentage was seen in grade levels 11 and 12.

According to the gathered data, it appears that both Science teachers and Non-Science Teachers have a high awareness of the concept and definition of Climate Change. For all survey questionnaire questions, science teacher and non-science teacher responses show that they are highly aware of the effects of climate change. However, in statements 3 and 5, 5.56% of the population of Science teachers responded that they were unaware of the effects of climate change, indicating that soil fertility won't be affected by it in the slightest and that what causes bodies of water to rise in level and sink a mass of land was climate change, which was also stated by scientists in their studies.

This implied that the level of awareness of the respondents' knowledge about climate change is high. The level of awareness in terms of concepts, ideas, causes, and effects of climate change of Science Teachers and Non-Science Teachers have no significant difference, yet this study is made to enrich the learning and assessment of Climate Change. The output drawn from the findings is a brochure entitled, "Awareness on Climate Change: The Educators' Point of View

The researcher advise carrying out environmental projects to support a healthy environment, such as the recycling of plastic bottles in the Yes-O project, a partnership between science and math students. The researchers also encourage us to continue this study and focus on the descriptive analysis of the differences between Science and Non-Science Teachers.

Since comprehension or understanding the different science-related terms is one of the important factors to prevent misconceptions, it is highly promoted to develop material that translates the different science terms and information that leads to a better understanding of the information stated.

CONCLUSION

The researcher concludes that the level of awareness in terms of concepts, definition, causes, and effects of climate change of Science Teachers and Non- Science Teachers have a minimal difference, yet it is proven that both Science Teachers and Non-Science Teachers has a high level of awareness in terms of concepts, definition, causes, and effects of climate change.

The researcher also concluded that now in the time being, both Science and Non- Science teachers have the knowledge and the awareness that a teacher must have towards climate change. It heightens the trust and the competency to start the step or progress to lessen the occurrence and future impacts of the phenomena in our environment.

REFERENCES

- Bhattacharya, D., Carroll Steward, K., & Forbes, C. T. (2021). Empirical research on K-16 climate education: A systematic review of the literature. *Journal of Geoscience Education*, 69(3), 223- 247.
- Competente, R. J. T. (2019). Pre-Service Teachers' Inclusion of Climate Change Education. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 8(1), 119-126.
- Gazzaz, N. M., & Aldeseet, B. A. (2021). Assessment of the Level of Knowledge of Climate Change of Undergraduate Science and Agriculture Students. *World Journal of Education*, 11(5), 41-60.
- Nation, M. T., & Feldman, A. (2022). Climate Change and Political Controversy in the Science Classroom: How Teachers' Beliefs Influence Instruction. *Science & education*, 31(6), 1567-1583.
- Pörtner, H. O., Roberts, D. C., Adams, H., Adler, C., Aldunce, P., Ali, E., ... & Ibrahim, Z. Z. (2022). *Climate change 2022: impacts, adaptation and vulnerability*. IPCC.

Declaration of Conflicting Interest. There are no conflicts concerning this research paper, authorship, and publication.

Funding. No funding from external sources, such as donations or grants, was received for conducting research, authorship, and publication of this paper.